

CHAPTER-II

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter discusses the literature in the context of Tourism Education globally; Tourism Education in India; Tourism, Tourism Education and Employment; Human Resource in Tourism Industry; Tourism Education and Tourism Planning; Tourism Education and Professionalism; Tourism Education and Sustainability; Problems in Tourism Education; Future of Tourism Education, Tourism Education Curriculum and Skills; and Research Gap.

Figure 2.1: Scheme of Literature Review

2.1: Tourism Education Globally: An Overview
2.2: Tourism Education in India
2.3: Tourism Education and Tourism Planning
2.4: Human Resource in Tourism Industry
2.5: Tourism Education and Tourism Planning
2.6: Tourism Education and Professionalism
2.7: Tourism Education and Sustainability
2.8: Problems in Tourism Education
2.9: Future of Tourism Education
2.10: Tourism Education Curriculum and Skills
2.11: Research Gap

Source: Literature review

2.1 Tourism Education Globally: An Overview

Tourism Education in the United Kingdom started in 1972 (Airey, 2005), In the Netherlands, secondary level tourism and leisure education started in 1978 (Venema, 2005). North America started its tourism education programs in 1940s

(Koh, 1994), in Germany tourism education was initiated in 1945 (Freyer et al. 2005). Uganda in 1994, Tanzania in 1969 while the economic cooperation among east African countries initiated in 1938 through a regional tourism policy. While Moi University in Kenya has multiple specialisation programs including Tourism policy and Planning (Mayaka, 2005). According to Zhang and Fan (2005), tourism education in China has reached the third phase as of its first phase was 1949-1978. Pattullo (1996) analyses that the Caribbean States can have economic development through tourism and human resources development in tourism field. Mustajarvi and Bouchon (2014) have advocated incorporation of regional alliance in context of tourism education in Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) region. The Indian hospitality education was started in 1954 and tourism education was started in 1952 (literature review).

a) Asia

As per the opinions of Mustajarvi and Bouchon (2014), “In the current age of globalization, regional alliances have become the norm, strengthening economic, political and social ties” (p.215). They suggested that there should be tourism education integration as well in ASEAN because “The higher education integration is a process which aims to harmonize the educational practices of different countries in order to form a system that is similar, thus, producing results which are comparable. This process usually involves mobility of students and faculty, research collaboration, common diploma supplement, recognition of qualifications, sharing resources, quality assurances and creation of common qualification structures” (Mustajarvi and Bouchon, 2014, p.216). The regional alliance of organisations is promoting scholarship in higher education because it leads to cross-fertilization of ideas through interaction among students, scholars and academics. During the academic year 2015-16, Maldives offered scholarship under South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) Scholarship Chair, to all member states in the field of tourism (Bachelor of Tourism Management). According to SAARC, member states are agree to promote regional cooperation vocational education and training. There is not any grounded strategy to explore the potential of youth in the field of tourism. Even ASEAN countries are promoting the regional cooperation among tourism education institute but limited and restricted too. European tourism education cooperation is

meeting the demands of economy and have expanded network (Mustajarvi and Bouchon, 2014). It can be inferred that ASEAN countries are lagging behind to tap the potential unlike European countries.

b) Australasia

King and Craig-Smith (2005), has revealed that tourism education in Australia is offered at different levels, high schools and secondary colleges, vocational education and training (VET), universities, private colleges and “in house” industry training. Travel agency training originated in Australia in the mid -1960s. Undergraduate tourism education started in Australia in the early 1970s in Victoria and Queensland it was mentioned by Wise (1978, cited King and Craig-Smith, 2005). And postgraduate programs started in late 1990s. They concluded Australia as tourism leader for trained tourism personals, Australian government plays a major role in exporting the tourism education under Sustainable Tourism Co-operative Research Centre (STCRC). STCRC was established by Commonwealth Governments in 1997. It is a network of Universities, private sectors and Governments, as well as this network provides a sound research platform for tourism education, there is government funding agency, Australian Research Council (ARC) as well as private stakeholders, it has enhanced the research output as well as collaboration among 15 universities. International Centre of Excellence in Tourism and Hospitality Education (ICE-THE), It isa 4-year program involves the collaboration among 15 University, STCRC members and Tertiary and Further Education (TAFE) New South Wales, it aims to enhance the creditability of Australia as an international centre of excellence in tourism and hospitality. In Australia, higher education is represented by Council of Australian Universities Tourism and Hospitality Education (CAUTHE). According to Pearce (2005), higher tourism education in Australia in context of global tourism education is has a benchmark and more famous. Also, identified that research-education network, coherence with pass outs, new tourism educators with bachelor and masters from tourism background, generic list of institution wise and multicity campus or multination campuses.

c) Brazil and Latin America

Leal and Padilha (2005), have described that tourism education and research in tourism domain in Latin American countries is still in budding stages. Research

revealed the explosion of undergraduate programs will lead towards first step of maturity. Growth of communication technology has connected the Latin American researchers' community to the international tourism researchers. Tourism industry of Latin America has shortages of man power in the field of foreign languages, marketing and information technology, and tourism education is seen as problematic issues because the region has lack of qualified human resources. Tourism Education taught in the institutions is irrelevant because it doesn't fulfil the real need of industry. Tourism Education as higher education (4 year bachelor degree and onward) in Brazil started in 1971 at Sao Paulo (largest city of Brazil). Tourism related modules were incepted in other subjects before 1971, it was different from North American and European. Brazil developed Tourism Education program as creation of program as foundation of tourism education in the country. The 1980s Latin American economic crisis lead to new Tourism Education program in Brazil. The 1990s neoliberalism led to a few more Tourism Education program, it was distinction of Tourism Education by Ansarah (2002) and development of programs increased more than 900% between 1994-2005. Teixeira (2001) in his research and present programs are based on balance between quality and quantity.

d) The Caribbean

Lewis (2005) has a critical analysis about the Caribbean tourism education and development of human resources for the futuristic changes. Pattullo (1996) finds out that governments and leaders of the Caribbean States have realised that tourism industry is the only means of economic survival. During 1995-2005, there has been political, technological and environmental changes in the region and these changes have challenged the academia to reassess the tourism education and training in the region. Tourism Education has been identified as an integral component for sustainability of tourism in the region. In the region, tourism education curriculum for tourism graduates is based on the quality assurance and adequately prepared for environmental, technological and political changes. Seward and Spinrad (1982) observed 1961-1970 as great optimism for the potential of tourism industry in the region. Lewis, (2005) explains that the University of West Indies in 1977 started degree program, to educate, train and prepare the Caribbean students to lead the hospitality and tourism industry in the region. It is the prime institute to preparing the

graduates to handle the management roles in the region. Before 1983 hospitality management programs were dominating but In 1983 Bachelor degree in Tourism Management was introduced for the wider tourism development issues. There is Association of Caribbean Tertiary Institutions (ACTI) under which University of West Indies has collaboration with Barbados community college, Antigua State College, College of Bahamas and the Trinidad and Tobago Hospitality and Tourism Institute, they offer 4-year BSc Degree in Hospitality and Tourism Management. For first two years degree is called Associate Degree in Hospitality and Tourism Management. Students can join any of the institute for next two years for specialisation in Hotel and Restaurant Management (Bahamas), Food, Beverages and Catering Management (Bahamas), Events and Entertainment Management (Trinidad), Tourism Product Management (Jamaica and Barbados) and Eco-tourism Site Management (Trinidad). This is a point of learning which is missing in majority of Indian tourism education institutes. It will lead to the collaboration among research and tourism stakeholders

e) China

Zhang and Fan (2005), identified that modern leisure tourism in China began after China's economic reform in 1978, and in the same year full-time Tourism Education was started in Jiangsu (Now Nanjing) Tourism Technical School. Before 1978 there was only on-job training and no tourism schools and colleges. First Tourism Education institution for higher learning was established in 1979 and it was named as Shanghai Institute of Tourism. These establishments of institutions propelled the mushrooming of tourism institutes like Sichun Tourism School, Guilin Specialised Tourism Institute, and Beijing Institute of Tourism with full-time tourism programs. The China National Tourism Administration (CNTA), is the administrative as well as funding body for several universities like Dalian Foreign Language Institute, Nanki University and Northwest University. These universities fulfil the need of tourism professionals with higher education background. Years of 1990s were a fast development time period for Tourism Education in China. China has a national-wide network of tourism vocational training and has three levels state, local and enterprises. Tourism Education was developed in *three phases*. *First phase (1949-1978)* started with the independence of China in 1949 and ended with the beginning of economic

reforms in 1978, during this phase tourism education was mainly to the hotel attendant, coach drivers, interpreters and guides, it was an adaptive training of the basic skill for a job given by individual enterprises or organisations (Tao, 1997). In this phase, travel and tourism was considered as a part of the reception work of foreign affairs. In *second phase* (1978-1995), tourism education was developed so fast and there was need for professionals because China's tourism was transforming from reception work of foreign affairs to an industry of economic returns. During this transforming phase, 138 institutions of higher learning and 484 secondary vocational schools were founded with more than 20 programs which offered tourism education and were categorised as tour-guiding, management, techniques and teacher-training. *Third phase* started from 1995 to present, during this phase Tourism Education transformed from planned economy to market economy and has entered the big tourist destination. Tourism institutions are focused on research, scientific setup of programs, cooperation and exchange program with foreign institutes and integration with international practices. In comparison to *second phase*, China's tourism education has slowed down in *third phase* because focus has been shifted to quality improvement and industry needs (CNTA, 2003). Tourism research projects in china are funded by the state, local and tourist enterprises. It concludes that there is need for continuum change in curriculum, student exchange program, teacher training and government and industrial support in terms of monetary. It can be more fruitful to have student exchange program or academic tour to the target market.

f) East Africa

Mayaka (2005) has explained through research work that Economic Commission for Africa (ECA) has recognised that regional cooperation among continents' countries is important for the optimum use of resources and development of human resources. According to Sindiga, (1999) the cooperation in tourism among East Africa countries could traced back in 1938 when a common tourism policy within the region began to emerge. Tourism Education in Kenya started in 1969 through hotel management courses at Kenya Polytechnic. For deep understanding about education and training of tourism, Swiss and Kenyan government established Kenya Utalii College (KUC). KUC admits local as well as 40 foreign students (Sindiga, 1999). The Moi University is the prominent university in Kenya which has three specialised departments namely;

Tourism (policy and planning), Travel and Tour Operations Management, and Hospitality and Hotel Management. Tourism research is lacking due to funding, motivation and focus as well as scarcity of qualified human resources. Tourism Education and training in Tanzania is less developed than Kenya. The National College of Tourism in Dar-es-Salaam was established in 1969. It offers certificate courses in Housekeeping, Laundry, Food and Beverage Sales, Food Production, and Front Office Operation. Premier Institute of Tanzania is College of African Wildlife Management was established in 1963 and college has maintained a regional outlook both in its organisation and approaches to curriculum development and delivery. Uganda is the late comer in Tourism Education establishment among three of East African countries. The Crested Crane Hotel and Tourism Training Institute in Jinja was established in 1994 to offer highest level of professional qualification and standards for the tourism industry. Nikuba University was the first to offer Tourism Education in 1994.

g) Germany

Freyer et al. (2005) explained Tourism Education started in Germany in 1945 and before that only a few universities, teachers and scientists were concerned with tourism research and Tourism Education. With the boom of travel in 1960s, first time advance courses for tourism managers were developed in context of business economics, political economics and geography at universities and Fachhochschulen (similar to polytechnic). In 1971, Fachhochschulen of Munich established the first curriculum for tourism in Germany in context of business economics. Universities, Fachhochschulen and academies of cooperative education (berufsakademien) provide tourism education through combination of part-time and full-time programs. Universities provide a 4-year (eight semester) course and 1-year post graduate programmes with a tourism specialisation. Fachhochschulen provides 3-year or 4-year course with a tourism, travel and hotel management specialisation. And Berufsakademien offers 1-year full time or 3-year part-time course. German universities provide Tourism Education as a compulsory, optional or specialised subject. Post graduate studies in tourism are mainly focused on those who are already in tourism industry and interested in high level management and doctorate.

h) The Netherlands

Venema (2005) provided an overview about tourism education in the Netherlands. In the Netherlands, education institutes are of two types public and private (not for profit) such as: Tourism Education is provided at secondary vocational level, higher vocational level and university level. Secondary Level Tourism and Leisure Education (Middelbaar Toeristisch en Recreatief Onderwijs-MTRO) was started in 1978. Dutch government allowed the Regional Training Centres (ROCs) to decide for themselves which type of education they want to offer, there are 40 ROCs with a MTRO department. At MTRO, students are educated for Travel (job at travel agency and wholesalers) and Tourism information (jobs at tourism information centre). First Higher Vocational Education Level (HBO, it's a four year program) was established in 1966 and till 2000 National College for Tourism and Transportation was the only institute of its kind in the Netherlands. Since the 1980s, Tilburg University has had an independent department of Leisure Studies. There are other universities like Groningen University and Nijmegen University that pay much attention to the various aspects of tourism recreation and leisure. The Netherlands' priority for international co-operation focuses on European Union (EU) and outside EU (Indonesia, China and South Africa) to attract international students.

i) North America

According to Koh (1994) in North America tourism as a subject was started in 1940s but subject development started in 1980s. Tourism studies and hospitality management are so deeply integrated in the USA and Canada so that it is hard to make generalisation. Jafari (2003), has mentioned that Michigan State University was the first to start Tourism Education in US in 1963. In 1970s, there were 40, 4-year degree programs in tourism. In Canada, there is a centralised system to have the information about different tourism programs at different institutions (Hudson, 2005).

j) The United Kingdom

According to Airey (2005), Tourism Education in the United Kingdom started in 1972 with introduction of two post graduate programs at the University of Strathclyde and the University of Surrey. The first two undergraduate programs were started in 1986.

It can be inferred from the above discussion that the countries which are performing well in tourism education; they have student exchange programs, continuum change in curriculum, regional wise tourism policy, reskilling of stakeholders, stable governments, working on national image building and diversifying tourism education. The institutional alliance at international, national and regional levels can create a pool of knowledge creating, experience sharing, network among stakeholders of tourism industry and national level platform to create an inventory of human resource, desired/ready to synergise the tourism industry. It is evident from the world history that tourism education results into 'change' after every pandemic or recession.

2.2 Tourism Education in India

Tourism higher education in the country is provided through Universities, colleges, AICTE affiliated institutes, NCHMCT approved organisations and Ministry of Tourism affiliated IITMs, centre for Tourism Studies, state owned independent institutes and NITHM. Indian Institute of Management Sirmour (IIMS) has invited application for MBA (T and HM) for session 2020-2022. Tourism education has developed along the development of tourism (inbound/domestic) industry. Kurukshetra University was the first to recognise and to adopt tourism education in 1991 formally (Singh and Singh, 2005). Himachal Pradesh University started Master of Tourism Administration in 1992. Institute of Hotel Management, Mumbai (2019) has mentioned through the institutional website that the institute was established in 1954, first of its kind in South East Asia. The institute started its programme with six students. This institute is called father or mother of hospitality education in the country. The starting of tourism education in country is recognised with Delhi University. The College for Vocational Studies was the first college to start tourism education in 1972 (Singh and Singh, 2005) and followed by Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University in 1976 (central university since 2009). This university started Post Graduate Diploma in Tourism and Pilgrimage Studies. In 1972 Tourism Education program was started at Centre for Vocational Studies, University of Delhi and course was devoted to train personal for ticketing and guiding services. As per the information from Shodhganga (2018), it was mentioned in National Committee on Tourism 1986 reported tourism is a national product that is not limited by State or

regional boundaries or other barriers. This realisation was necessary to avoid distortions in our perceptions and policies. Hence, there was need for a national consensus on the role and level of tourism development in the country. The Committee recommended that for the development of human resource, universities should be encouraged to adopt tourism oriented courses. Institutes like Indian institute of management (IIM) should have separate departments to fulfil the need of management in tourism services, training facilities for first level staff. This training can be provided by IIMs, universities and hotel institutes. The Committee also recommended to setup 'Culinary Institute of India' to train chef manpower. Culinary Institute of India was established with a name Indian culinary institute at Tirupati (2016) and Noida (2018). Further, A list of generic skills developed by universities as per with location and courses offered by the university as per the instruction from government. Tourism education at managerial level is determined by university in context of values, resources, support, employability and future of the course. In addition, "critical thinking and problem-solving, working with others, communication, numeracy, information technology awareness, life-long learning orientation, social and cultural awareness and civic responsibility" (Pearce, 2005, pp.259-260). Chaudhary and Saraswat (2009) argued that tourism will increase in future and 'this would mean more service providing firm rather than service providing individuals'. Further 'Tourism supply is a largely local phenomenon' but the transmigration of unemployed youth from one part of the country to other part (which have shortage of professionals).

According to Dahiya (2013), "Indian tourism and hospitality education has a multifaceted outlook and can be divided into three periods: the origination period (1950–1970), the infancy period (1970–1990), and the growth and competition period (1990–present)" (p.365). If tourism education and hospitality education are considered as distinct (Dahiya, 2013) entity it leads to the conclusion that 1950-1970 was not origination period for tourism education. The UNWTO.TedQual Certification (2013) reported that there are only two Higher Tourism Education Programmes certified by UNWTO in India which are Post Graduate Diploma in Travel and Tourism Administration at Centre for Tourism Studies (CTS) Jaipur. And Bachelor in Tourism Administration and Master in Tourism Administration offered by Institute of Travel and Tourism, Amity University. CST has this accreditation because they offer

foreign exchange programme, multination culture, multination placement, and established by Rajasthan Chamber of Commerce. On the other side, Institute of Travel and Tourism, has multinational campus, availability of modern infrastructure, industry like settings, and strong links with industry and practice of sustainability, destination knowledge and global experiences are the outcomes of the learnings as well as behavioural science and foreign business languages. International Institute of Hotel Management is registered with World Tourism Education Directory because of its multinational campuses, dual degree, overseas career and alumni network of more than 10000 and for proactive curriculum. Thakur (2014) has revealed “Tourism industry in India is encountering an acute shortage of right type of manpower, improper training and education programs of tourism sector is discouraging right type of skilled and talented people” (p.7). Besides, explored that tourism industry as well as academia is faulty because no recruitment policy, no specific requisite qualification, no specialist in this profession moreover there is no updated programs in tourism academia. Establishment of Indian Institute of Tourism Management (IITTM) started the era of Tourism Education in India in 1983 and became the apex body of tourism education but scarcity of specialised programs offered by IITTM

There are Central Universities and State Universities (which are higher in number) are providing tourism education in the country. Indian tourism education programs are general in nature, which are centred around Tourism and Hospitality only. The only difference is that these programs are available in the form of certificate course, diploma course, Undergraduate, Post Graduate, MPhil and PhD. Countries like Australia have a diverse educational program in tourism as and ranking of tourism education taking in consideration of teaching locations, generic skills and graduate attributes, educator competence, human resource planning and how to assess performance (Pearce, 2005). According to Dange (2016), involvement of parents, administrators, politicians, reformers, planners and educationists in the development of education at all levels can lead to quality education. This networking can also help in bridging the quantity and quality of education in Indian higher education system. Moreover, the rate of curriculum reforms and pedagogical reforms can align with the advancement of knowledge. Further, digital literacy among teachers, reformed evaluation systems and networking of universities can lead to the quality education. As per online website Reviewadda (2018) Tourism Management is 13th most popular

course in India after 10+2 while Hospitality Management is ranked at 6th position. The website has mentioned key personalities in the concerned field. But tourism course has no key personality mentioned. Moreover, Central Board of School Education (CBSE, 2019) has included Tourism and Travel course in Compendium of Academic Courses after +2. CBSE has defined Tourism education as “it studies the physical, economic, social and cultural aspects of tourism, tourist markets, and destination. It also studies the wider perspective of tourism as interdisciplinary way drawing knowledge from several social science subjects” (p.113). There are 14204 senior secondary schools affiliated to CBSE in the country till May 2019. National Skill Development Corporation has identified Travel and tourism as stream, in which central government is providing skills to cater the industry demand and enhance the employment opportunities to unemployed (NSDC, 2019). It will definitely promote tourism education. But the organisation has wrongly described the criteria of eligibility. Which makes a question mark on the organisation about knowledge to get admission in Travel and Tourism course. Because the eligibility is over demanded than required one. Tourism educators around the globe are producing different skills through tourism education among the pupils. Moreover, nature of tourism education is different in different countries and continents. Further, Tourism education in Europe focused on training and apprenticeship, American tourism education on Managerial science and Asian tourism education on innovation and service quality. Expansion of tourism industry has led to the development of tourism education programme in Asian countries (Liu and Schänzel, 2019).

The transmigration concept can be applied among countries among tourism students. As well as Tourism Education Expert from other countries can be hired for some interval of time to channelize the Tourism Education along with contemporary global industry demand but under the government control. It is leading towards the internationalisation of tourism education and employment. Host/local tourism service providers should be educated (tourism) so they can sustain their livelihood throughout the year.

2.3 Tourism, Tourism Education and Employment

The tourism industry is a multiproduct industry (Diamond, 1977). It has raised the demand for a skilled manpower in tourism industry and consequently tourism

education and training to get employed in tourism industry (Department of Tourism, 1992). The growth of international tourism arrival, economy and shift in education policy boosted tourism education in Australia during the mid-1980s and led to employment generation. Tourism activities are an integral part of tourism and these activities provide employment to the service providers (Hobson, 1995). According to Riley et al. (2002), the tourism industry provides employment from macro to a small unit, tourism industry is fragmented and dominated by small units, being a labour-intensive industry continuum training and education of employees is needed in tourism industry. They added, in developing countries the younger generation is more inclined towards tourism industry jobs than traditional employment. The attractive aspect of a large proportion of tourism jobs is that it involves direct contact with customers (Riley et al. 2002). Leal (2004), has noted that Brazilian tourism education came into existence during the liberalization of economies in the 1990s and tourism sector also. The researcher added sustainability of tourism education and industry in the country, universities are diversifying the courses and government favouring employability of tourism graduates in industry. Moreover, instability of government is a critical issue for growth in tourism employment. While Busby (2005) major reason to adopt tourism programs is employment. Pearce (2005), has clearly opined that tourism industry provides a variety of jobs in different sectors (private or public) and require different skills, knowledge and network. The researcher revealed the United Kingdom and Europe is a specialist in Leisure Studies; the United States is a specialist in Park and Recreation programs. Tourism education generates employment in the commercial sector, the education and training sector, and the public and facility management sector. In New Zealand, those who are not interested in higher studies they are equipped with tourism and hospitality industry based skills to provide them employment (King and Craig-Smith, 2005). As Tribe (2005) mentioned that, tourism is a phenomenon which comprises of experiences and events accepted by human mind. Tourism activities are the part of tourism phenomena and they generates employment. While emergence of tourism programs helps in specialization of human resources and tourism as a body of knowledge makes it a discipline. The emergence of discipline shows the demand for programs and consequently generates employment at different levels of performance or management of activities. Diversification of programs specialization is an important dimension to enhance the employability of

tourism graduates. Inui et al. (2006), Tourism employment varies from sector to sector. It demands different skills and academic knowledge and its applications. Employment in tourism industry is transmigration (Chaudhary and Saraswat, 2009) i.e. workforce transmigrate from one region (country) to professional deficient region (country). The robust performance of international tourism is contributing to economic growth and job creation in many parts of the world. The tourism industry has become an academic study and a global network of researchers (Taillon, 2014). It is leading to knowledge creation and helping diversify the tourism product and its benefits. Vijayaraghvan (2014) concluded tourism is an important resource of foreign exchange and there is a need for tourist and foreign investment centric policies. It is clear from the argument of Sheldon and Hsu (2015) that “tourism employment in the coming decades will have a very different profile than it does today. For example, the key jobs in 2015 might not even exist today, and much of what we teach our students may be obsolete by the time they graduate” (p.63). It is thus critical for countries to promote policies that foster the continued growth of tourism, including travel facilitation, human resources development and sustainability (Rifai, 2016). According to Medium (2018), tourism is providing employment to island nations to landlocked countries and tourism is playing a leading role in employment generation in economically weaker countries. Tourism has employment opportunities for low skilled human resources across the globe, but the advancement in technology can have a severe impact on the low skilled employees. The travel and tourism industry employs a higher proportion of women than other sectors; irrespective of the size of the national economy.

Hence, it is clear from the above discussion that Tourism is reaching the unreached and providing income and employment and leading to destination development. The benefits of tourism industry are not limited to employment generation because tourism industry provides a good infrastructure to the local community and it empowers women. It was found that vocationalisation of tourism education led to employment generation and not making human resource (tourism graduates) creative and reflective. It shows that there is a need to diversify tourism education, reskilling of tourism stakeholders because of technological advancement. The pandemic like COVID-19 has adversely impacted the tourism sector, future

tourism education and tourist behaviour as well. Hence, there is need to revamp the existing tourism education system to overcome the dynamics of global tourism.

2.4 Human Resource in Tourism Industry

Amoah and Baum (1997) have investigated human resource is the foundation of tourism industry. Peacock and Ladkin, (2002), asserted that “At the macro level, the improvement of the human resource will result into a national gain, and at the micro-level businesses and enterprises will benefit from a better-trained workforce and knowledge transferal. The students themselves will also be better prepared to face future challenges if educators and industry leaders work together” (p.394). This implies that there is a need to integrate tourism education policy with national tourism development policy. McDonald and Hopkin (2003) have advocated that specialised education leads to the quality of the human resource is concerned industry. Stevenson (2004) advocated the integration of theory and practices of tourism education the researcher added: “Seminars can provide learning opportunities to explore, experience and engage with subject material and to make connections between theory and practice” (p.107). It can play a role to enhance critical thinking and application of knowledge. Manpower with digital skills are also needed in the era of digitalisation (Buhalis and Law 2008). Sheldon et al. (2011) have mentioned that TFFI has advocated adopting value-based tourism education comprises of ethics, professionalism, mutuality, stewardship and knowledge. The outcome of these basics values for tourism programs across the world to be a responsible representative-cum-leader of tourism and travel system. Ethics leads to transparent decision making, knowledge gained by creativity, professionalism, incorporating problems solving temperament, stewardship quality to serve the host community and responsibilities of the stakeholders and mutuality towards lifelong learning. The growth in tourism industry impressively leads to the demand of efficient manpower (Dahiya, 2013). Hence, it is clear that there is a need to develop multi-dimensions among tourism graduates with regards to values and skills.

Indian tourism industry has potential to grow but there is lack of qualified human resources at operational and managerial level (Dhanoa, 2014). Vijayaraghvan (2014), for the sustainability of tourism industry trained manpower is required at managerial, supervisory and skilled or semi-skilled based operation. There is dearth of

human resource at mid and senior management levels of the organizations. Further, this gap is raised because of lack of tourism training infrastructure, educator as well as lifelong strategies and policies (p.2836). Ghatage and Kumbhar (2015) proposed the central and state governments should provide qualified personnel and training for human resource working in tourism industry.

As per the information from the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (2018); hospitality and tourism sector was considered as priority sector in 2014-2015 to provide the skilled manpower to industry. Internationally competitive and skilled manpower can shine India as a tourism leader. Tourism and Hospitality Skill Council (THSC, 2018) has a target to skill 3.3 million manpower by 2022. The common goal of above-mentioned organisation is to cater the employers with skilled manpower. Even THSC has identified there is an ever-growing gap between industry requirement and manpower supplied. To link education to employment engagement with industry of students at all levels of higher education be appropriately exposed to social and industrial development of surroundings. There is a statistical difference in the perception towards oral communication skills, written communication skills, leadership ability, research skills, creativity, computer skills, problem-solving skills, and work ethics between tourism academicians and tourism professionals (Nagarjuna, 2016). Contemporary skills in human capital are essential for the survival of the tourism industry. As per United Nations World Tourism Organisation (2018), totalled 1.4 billion international tourist arrivals (+6%), consolidating 2017 strong results and proving to be the second strongest year since 2010. Digitalisation, new business models, more affordable travel and societal changes are expected to continue shaping tourism sector. So, destinations and travel companies need to be continuum to a player in the industry. As well as the interaction among industry and higher education institution, so that human resources can be easily placed in the industry (Nimse, 2016). The Learning agility, result orientation and interpersonal skills are preferred skills in tourism industry (UNDP India skills report, 2017) from the human resource. It is the responsibility of tourism education to produce quality human resource. Tourism education across the globe has developed through different dimensions. European tourism education focused on training and apprenticeship, American on Managerial science and Asian on innovation and service quality (Liu and Schanzel, 2019). The tourism industry is growing as international

tourist arrival is on growth. Tourism industry demands a different type of human resources e.g. Liu and Schanzel (2019) In Indonesia industry search for 'job-ready' people irrespective of skill level and educational background.

In addition, the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Report (2019) has expressed that travel and tourism policies towards sustainable development of tourism in India ranked 34th (140) globally and 6th in Asia Pacific region. The rich cultural and natural heritages and price competitiveness are the leading factors to place India 6th in Asia Pacific region. In Asia Pacific region India has shown a strong improvement in business environment, environmental sustainability, cultural resources and business travel. But globally, India still needs to enhance its enabling environment (98th), tourist service infrastructure (109th) and environmental sustainability (128th). With regards to effective development of human resource its efficient use, India stands at 76th rank among 140 economies. Undoubtedly, India has good ranking in airport transportation infrastructure (33), ground and port transportation (28th), but high-quality human resource recognise the need of the industry. As per the Incredible India Tourist Facilitator Certification (IITFC, 2020) Programme, government, tourism business, education institute, tourism and trade associations, tourism trade media, human resource and host population are key actors of tourism (IITFC, 2020). Tourism education institution work as a source of human resources for tourism businesses, because they train and develop human resource as per the tourism industry demand. Tourism education in India is being taught from schools to universities, full time to short term courses, certificates to degree and private as well as government universities. As per IITFC (2020), NCHMCT, Indian Institute of Tourism and Travel Management(s), Indian Institute of Skiing and Mountaineering and Indian Culinary Institute are supported by Ministry of Tourism, Government of India to produce human resource across the country.

It can be inferred from the above analysed literature that development and growth of tourism industry depend upon the skilled human resources. The opinions have also found in favour of specialisation based tourism education for sustainable development of tourism. The macro-scale improvement in tourism education leads to national benefits and at a micro level, it fulfils the needs of employers. There is a need for an academia-industry network to improve the performance of human resource.

The skills demanded by this labour-intensive industry vary from country to country or destination to destination. India is full of resources (beaches, heritages, island, mountains, and nature) which can be developed and promoted across the globe through diversification of tourism education programs. The Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Report (2019) has already found that India is not among the top 105 countries in context of tourist service infrastructure. The researcher found that there is a demand-supply mismatch. Hence it implies that there is an immediate need to improve tourist services and consequently need to redesign curriculum, use of technology, organising seminars and conferences for theory and practice of being taught, development entrepreneurship bent of mind among tourism graduates in higher studies and promotion of knowledge creation and its application. The separate tourism education board with regional branches and lifelong learning among tourism stakeholders can be an ice-breaking step in tourism industry.

2.5 Tourism Education and Tourism Planning

According to Silver and Brennan (1988), the vocational curriculum in tourism education creates employment in the tourism industry but it does not provide 'thinking and reflection'. Tribe (2005) has advocated tourism is a phenomenon of activities and events of human mind acceptance. It has attracted academicians towards knowledge creation and called it a 'study of tourism'. The author termed the knowledge of tourism as 'problematic' and suggested for 'choice of knowledge' instead of an induction program in higher tourism education. It can be inferred from his work that the participation of academicians towards knowledge creation in the field of tourism gives rise to tourism education and training to facilitate the industry. As per the information from Shodhganga (an academic repository), National Committee on Tourism 1986, the committee was established by the Planning Commission to prepare a perspective plan for the tourism sector headed by Mr Mohammed Yunus and its recommendations were given in November 1987. It suggested that there should be a separate cadre of professionals to look after the functioning of the tourism board. National Action Plan on Tourism (1992), came with one of the objectives to achieve 1% (.4% in 1992) foreign tourist arrival of globally and by the end of the year 2000 (2.65 million) as per the Ministry of Tourism. The researchers, Amoah and Baum (1997) have found that tourism environment (features

and products of tourism, the tourism industry, tourism industry markets, and the impact of tourism on the locality or country) and world of tourism education are dynamic and influenced by environmental, political and economic and socio-cultural factors. Further, tourism education should be aligned with national tourism policy. It is possible through the cooperation of tourism policymakers and tourism education policymakers. It can lead to practical tourism education and its desired outputs.

Figure 2.2: The TEP-TEI Conceptual Framework

Source: Amoah and Baum (1997)

TEP-Tourism education Policy, TEI-Tourism education Implementation

Tribe (1997), curriculum’s vocational component is influenced by those who have commercial interest while, environmentalist, local community encourages liberal component. McKercher (2002) had speculated that if a university has a quality of staff, use of technology, positioning the tourism program in the tourism industry, developing leadership quality among individual tourism graduates and the ability of the university to attract the faculty of other universities show that tourism education providers are committed to quality tourism education. Also, the quality of academicians can be improved by the upskilling of academic staff, either through staff turnover or the upgrading of academic qualifications.

Furthermore, practical based programmes offered by industry practitioners while the academic field of study taught by scholars lead to quality education. To compete with the contemporary global scenario, universities encourage existing staff to enhance their academic qualifications or had to find new staff with appropriate qualifications who wish to develop careers in tourism academia. Besides, Lewis (2004) conducted a study on tourism curriculum development in the Caribbean Islands and found that the following bent of mind is requisite as a curriculum output by stakeholders. Tourism curriculum must have outputs as managerial skills, a benchmark of quality services, transferable skills, flexibility and critical thinking, universal understanding of tourism and to develop the understanding among the tourism graduates towards a role in national development and tourism be an integral part of tourism planning. Lewis (2004), explored that there should be a balance between vocational as well as liberal tourism education. Tourism students “must be prepared to work in tourism and for tourism” (Lewis, 2004, p.83).

Table 2.1: Curriculum Content

Vocational Action	Liberal Action
Tourism Marketing HR Management Business Development Foreign Languages Entrepreneurship Quality Service Information Technology	Liberal Action Tourism and Environment Planning and development Sustainable tourism
Problem Solving Creative Thinking	Tourism and Politics Culture and Heritage
Reflective Vocational	Reflective Liberal

Source: Lewis (2004)

“The role and purposes of tourism education take on a new meaning that spans beyond the confines of the classroom and the work environment in the industry to embrace wider economic and socio-cultural issues that are important in the development of tourism and affect the livelihood of the locals in the society” ((Lewis, 2004, pp. 85-86).

Figure 2.3: The local context for curriculum

Source: Lewis (2004)

Lewis (2004), explored that Island stakeholders are into tourism business for economic profit, but to compete with the global competition they need training, it is Vocational Component of the curriculum. Tourism causes negative impact i.e. environmental and socio-cultural, to address these issues, there is a need for tourism planning, it makes the liberal component. The stakeholders want academicians to develop the curriculum that can make balance. There is a need to emphasis on vocational (there is a need for training of hired staff) as well as liberal (environment and community wellbeing need to be addressed) component of tourism education. Stevenson et al. (2008) asserts through his research that policymaking is essentially a social process, involving communication and negotiation between people in the context of wider change. A social conceptualisation, and further research to investigate the communication involved in producing policy rather than focus on the tangible outputs of the process such as a plan or a physical development. So, tourism planning is not about physical development at a destination. However, tourism studies do not exist as an integrated field of study. Instead, there are countless empirical accounts, case studies, approaches, theories and perspectives in individual disciplines, including economy, geography, psychology, architecture, ecology, sociology, political science and medicine (Gyr, 2010). Further, Samadhi Vibrations (2016) shared thoughts through Education Blooming a Child program and mentioned that there is a need for specialization based study after 12 years of education. Hence, there is need to adopt tourism education because human genius not performing because of the current education system. Cuffy et al. (2012) described, tourism destination cannot fully realise its potential or effectively continue to compete for regional and worldwide tourism without an educated workforce and high calibre human resource.

Furthermore, there are counted published works on tourism education across the globe and only edited books are available. The Hospitality Management Education (1999) edited by Barrows and Bosselman is among the first generation books published regarding tourism education, mostly from the North American perspective. The Global Tourism Higher Education: Past, Present, and Future (2005), edited by Hsu, An International Handbook of Tourism Education edited by Airey and Tribe in 2005. The newest published book on tourism education is Tourism Education and Asia. It is edited by Claire Liu Heike Schanzel (2019). It shows the fact that tourism education has spread around the world but the scarcity of tourism education-based book publication. Tourism education is a lifelong learning approach and focused on awareness and critical understanding of tourism among the population of the destination. Moreover, tourism education can be introduced from early childhood education and developed in a spiral fashion to tertiary, adult and continuing education and industry training. The South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC, 2019) has stated that education is fully essential to social and human development in its ability to transform lives.

Lewis, 2004 explored that “A tourism society where the development of tourism is planned, there is proper stewardship of the natural resources and the local culture is preserved” (p.83).A tourism education providing university commits resources, quality innovation, market place leadership and institutional magnetism towards other university faculty. Moreover, upskilling of present staff, hiring qualified staff with contemporary skills are the key point to vest academia with qualities. In the 21st century changed merely a construction of knowledge is not enough need to be implemented through networking to benefit the earth sustainability not only local community. Tourism education is the application of knowledge which comes from the ‘study of tourism’ and implementation of the knowledge for sustainable development (contemporary model of tourism development) of all the infrastructures of development. Tourism has become pivotal in developing and developed economies across the globe. It raises the need for redesigning the courses and curricula, in the context of bigger global issues to resolve the negative impacts of tourism and deal with poverty elevation, climate change and quality of life. Above literature again talks about the redesigning of courses curriculum and it is a global requirement.

2.6 Tourism Education and Professionalism

Professionalism has multifaceted dimensions i.e. growth of individual as well as organisation, lifelong learning, innovation and development of nation above all. As per the opinions of Hill et al (2013), the professionalism can be incorporated through education, training and motivation of aspiring professionals. Continuous learning ability is a major facet of professionalism. The professionalism behaviour is heavily influenced by changes in the political, cultural and economic context in which professionals work. Also economic loss to the local community is walking parallel with tourism growth, but it can be minimised through professional training among the locals. The fact is supported by the Oppermann (1993) who has revealed that “the import propensity or leakage factor depends mostly on the country’s economic structure for example, the level of technology, production of agricultural products, and education level of the local population” (p.549). The Ministry of Tourism (India) closed its Toronto based tourism office after 58 years in 2018 and assigned a reason of shifting the office to another region of the globe. But it has not shown its presence yet. It shows the lack of professionalism in the ministry.

Further, Singh (2001), has defined Tourism Education not a source to produce managers but effective entrepreneurs, specialist, interpreters and responsible citizens can be produced. Tan and Morgan (2001) explored that “Partnerships between educators and industry professionals can facilitate students’ tourism career opportunities” (p.59). Moreover Stevenson (2004) speaks, seminars can be designed to inculcate leadership and presentation skills among the students and as a bridge between academia and industry. Wickens and Forbes (2004), there is need to redefine the relationship, role, nature of relation between student and tutor. Gupta (2008) opined strongly, gap between tourism education and industry needs, leads to direct and indirect generation of poor quality of human resources, adverse impact on the economy and decline of tourism industry itself. The researcher mentioned, these three major consequences will emerge if gap analysis is not studied and relevant actions are not taken to bridge this gap. Above-mentioned literature identified the consequences which arise due to the gap between tourism education and industry needs but not mentioned the context of analysis of gap and those actions which are relevant to fulfil the gap between tourism education and industry needs. It can be inferred that there is

communication gap between academia and industry which results into supply-demand mismatch. There is urgent need of communication between academia and industry. It will definitely make a paradigm shift in while quality education can be an output towards professionalism. Technological innovation has changed the work culture of tourism business organisations, marketing strategy, product development, destinations and consumer centric technologies (Buhalis and Law 2008). In the context of transitional economics, education, networking, professional associations, international exposure and the development of a tourism professional identity are the fundamentals of professionalism in tourism industry (Hussey et al. 2011). Educator's responsibility is to lead the way more effectively, linkages and research will need to be established with special disciplines and professional practice careers at the academic and industry level. Moreover, Bagri and Babu (2011) Indian tourism education has not optimum share in tourism benefits as well as less professional compared to other continents. Sheldon et al. (2011), have mentioned that "*Professionalism* is defined as incorporating leadership, a practical approach (practicality), attention to services, concern for the relevance and timeliness of evidence, reflexivity, teamwork and partnership building skills, and pro-activity" (pp. 14-15). Besides it, Derouiche (2012) considers non-diversification and non-innovation of tourism product at a destination lead to decline of destination. Competitiveness in travel trade has led to the increasing demand of competitive tourism education and training (Dahiya, 2013). Also suggested that efficient human resource cannot be produced without institutional infrastructure and training facilities. It can be inferred that quality in tourism education is directly proportional to quality in human resource which can lead to the quality in tourism industry. Without quality tourism education and its implementation, manpower cannot lead to the desired outputs from tourism industry. The characteristics of a profession are outcome of empirical research. The efforts of all involved-students, faculty and employers can lead to professionalism.

Tourism is a global phenomenon, which involves different cultures and economies. The UNWTO is working on internationalisation of minds of future tourism professionals (UNWTO.TedQual, 2013). Correspondingly, tourism education must develop ability among tourism graduates to apply tourism knowledge in real time situations. Tourism is labour intense industry and "it is important for the tourism

industry to attract highly qualified workers with the skills and knowledge necessary to meet the requirements of employers in the tourism sector” (Wang, 2010, p.8).

In the same fashion, Thomas and Thomas (2013) explored that “Generally, empirical research has emphasized the perspectives of those with an interest in promoting the process of professionalising particular occupations” (p.3). “Professional associations played a critical part in the process of professionalization” (p.1). In corporate strategy of professionalisation, two possible developments are “perhaps most typically, organisations that employ professionals use their power to shape the values and practices of the profession. In this case, often termed ‘corporate professionalism’, the independence of professionals – notably in terms of how they deliver and evaluate their occupational activity – is reduced or lost (or there is a failure to professionalise). Alternatively, perhaps in fewer instances, the values and knowledge created by professions via their professional association may strengthen their status, influence and material rewards” (p.4). The corporate professionalism encircles specialized knowledge regarding the occupation and professionals’ multi-level entry. Comprehensively, tourism is growing for decades but there is deficiency of professionalism. Chen (2014), Chinese tourism industry is growing because of “economic development and relatively a stable society” (p.40). It can be inferred that stability of society leads to professional society. Hiring of qualified staff is need of the hour. The researchers Perman and Mikinac (2014) have also explored that “The overall quality within the hospitality and tourism sector depends exactly on education and training, i.e. the overall level of education of employed staff” (p.616). It implies quality of an industry depends on the overall level of education of employed staff. They analysed that in Republic of Croatia, there are limited number of training programs which can influence on education level and career of employed staff in tourism industry. Quality of service is an integral part of the tourism product and training and education of staff develop new value-added product and nourish professionalism. World class tourism professionals can be produced through students and teachers exchange programme (Nimse, 2016). It will broaden professional and academic experiences of teachers and students. The United Nations Development Program India skills report 2017 has concluded that Hospitality (Aviation, Travel and Tour, Hotels) sector hired manpower between age group of 18-21 years, with skill preferences learning agility, result orientation and Interpersonal

skills. Moreover, tourism managers demand for both specific skill/knowledge and personality (Stergiou and Airey, 2017). According to Dixit (2019) first book on tourism education was *Hospitality Management Education* (1999) edited by Barrows and Bosselman on North American perspective. Followed by *Global Tourism Higher Education: Past, Present, and Future* (2005), edited by Hsu, and *An International Handbook of Tourism Education* (2005), edited by Airey and Tribe. And the newest work on tourism education is *Tourism Education and Asia* (2019) edited by Claire Liu Heike Schanzel. And case study has proved that Asian Tourism education is focusing on more vocational or functional managerial knowledge. Advancement in technologies providing a challenge for continuum change in skills requirement, digital skills is one of them. Also, Institute of Hotel Management (2019), in order to compete on an international stage in the field of Hospitality Education - modern equipment, up-to-date curriculum and dedicated faculty is essential and imperative to attain and maintain global standards. "Tourism educational programs need to fundamentally retool and redesign—not incrementally by adding new courses or simply by putting courses on-line—but by changing the nature of what is taught and how it is taught. Skills and knowledge sets must be redefined. Structures and assumptions need to be questioned, and old ways of doing things must be transcended" (Sheldon et al, 2008 p.63).

The review of literature shows professionals association, academic-industry interaction and networking, quality education and lifelong learnings are the foundation of professionalism. The research and development, stable society and rich literature nourish the professionalism. The lack of professionalism is prevailing in tourism education system across the country and abroad.

2.7 Tourism Education and Sustainability

Importance of tourism education and sustainability is wider and unmeasurable to sustain the tourism industry. As Butler (1980) has found that without the practices of sustainability 'the most attractive and interesting areas in the world are doomed to become tourist relics '. Tourism education can play an important role to achieve sustainable destinations and tourism as well. It is widely agreed that education and training are important to the achievement of sustainable tourism (Cater and Goodall,

1992; Ham et al. 1991; Johnson, 1998). Tourism education can be more relevant to achieve sustainable tourism practices. According to Lane (1994), “Strategy-making can be used as a vehicle for new ideas and for the beginning of an ongoing educational process bringing new skills, and new flexibility into the business and political life of a region” (p.100). “A series of training and education courses should be offered to encourage new entrants to tourism and to help existing businesses” (p.109). Hunter (1997) described that sustainable tourism will occur through the adaptive approach of “Tourism Imperative”, “Product-Led Tourism”(p.860), “Environment-Led Tourism”(p.861) “Neotenous Tourism”(p.862),the participation of local community in decision making regarding tourism development projects and ecological conservation objectives selection with regards to community. Hunter (1997) defined Neotenous tourism as ‘an in which very little, or no, tourism is permitted’, it implies that controlled tourism activities are demanded.

Figure 2.4: Psychographic positions of destinations

←-----Rise to fall of a destination

Source: Plog, 2001

There is need to develop psychographic positions of destinations with in India, because Plog (2001), “Many unplanned destinations face a declining future because uncontrolled growth has discouraged influential Venturer type travellers” (p.21).Also revealed that “Self-confident and intellectually curious, Venturers have a strong desire to explore the world of ideas and places” (p.15).“Quality is an issue that is fundamental to all aspects of tourism education” (Tribe, 2002, p.73). Further, they suggested sustainable tourism can be a reality if practiced by introducing tourism and

environment program based specialization and, program's output at a destination. The above works implies that planning is an essential tool for sustainable development and it comes through incorporation of quality tourism education. The UNWTO (United Nations world tourism organisation) is practicing tourism keeping sustainable development goals as tool of development. Sharpley (2002) rural tourism in Cyprus, is an alternative to declining agrarian economies and tourism product diversification. Lack of technical assistance for rural entrepreneur is one of the challenges to promote rural tourism, while rural tourism an approach to practice sustainable tourism. Destination planning programs are missing in Indian tourism education and need to incorporate such programs, because Plog (2001) had revealed "If a destination's planners understand the psychographic curve, it is possible for them to control tourism development and to maintain an ideal positioning" (p.19).Bramwell (2010)is concerned on sustainability of tourism with three suggestions: examination of participative tourism planning, tourism planning should be contemporary (economically, socially and ideological circumstances) and more research attention to the broad range of contexts and activities of tourism governance. Bramwell (2010) supported, tourism planning should involve experts.The sustainability-driven minds being produced in Australian tourism academia. For sustainable development such minds need to be produced at regional, national and global level. Because sustainability works towards society as it has strands of intellectual thought including equity, limits to growth, nature, poverty (Schweinsberg et al. 2013). Perman and Mikinac (2014) "High-quality and sustainable development of tourism demands an efficient national policy of education and professional development" (p.617). Tourism and sustainability are closely linked and discussions about sustainability have a long history amongst tourism academics and practitioners (Moscardo, 2015).

Tourism education has an important role to develop sustainable tourism strategies as well as to encourage entrepreneurs in business establishment vis-à-vis to help established tourism enterprises. Tourism education is double edged with development as well as conservation. Tourism education can help to achieve sustainability of tourism through indigenous curricula. The corporate social responsibility through tourism education for sustainable tourism in higher education can produce graduates with a strong and developed sense of knowing about social responsibility, equity and justice. Further, one way to achieve these goals is through

indigenous curricula and it will increase the education participation of indigenous people. Indigenised curricula can also develop skills, knowledge and attitudes that enable all students to contribute to a multi-cultural society, with particular cultural sensitivity to Indigenous experiences (Young and Maguire, 2016).

Scheme for Promotion of Academic and Research Collaboration (SPARC) reimagining teacher education (n.d.), has explored that teachers are centre of sustainable development goals i.e. equity and quality education can be addressed by teachers and their work. Teacher training is a lifelong process and shouldn't be limited to early tenure of practices. Further, education is influenced by global professionals demand. Lifelong learning includes qualification as per profession, training, out of box thinking and career support. A sustainable world and future leaders can be developed through conceptual skills and research. Role of tourism education is not limited to produce manpower to cater tourism industry, but its responsibility enlarged to a great role to produce future leaders', who can lead all societies in sustainable practices. Tourism Education is the key player through which planner and researcher can make tourism planning, contemporary (economically, socially and ideological circumstances) and can research more critically.

2.8 Problems in Tourism Education

It was mentioned in the above discussion that rich literature is an important tool for professionalism. Also educator must be aware of needs of industry (Peacock and Ladkin, 2002) and problems responsible for non-interface of education.-industry. In addition, Tribe (2002) argued "indeed how does tourism higher education match up to other degree programmes? The lack of evaluative and prescriptive literature in this area is of prime concern" (p.73). It asserts that lack to 'tourism studies' based literature is a key problem in tourism education. Moreover, subject has 'humble origin', as the pioneer publication came into light the importance of subject sparked across the variety of education institution. It can be concluded that pioneer publication is very important for the publicity of subject. McKercher (2002), described Australian tourism education is facing problem .i.e. stratification of tourism programmes over prestige of institution. Moreover, academia has less industry experience and industry practitioner have less chances to practice as academia because of qualification.

It was explored by Shepherd and Cooper (1994), four main areas of interaction such as the need to identify industry requirements, work placement schemes, curriculum planning issues, and ways in which tourism educators can update their industry knowledge. The industry and academia interact in different ways. Botterill (1996) identifies six main areas: student placements, staff exchange and collaboration, industry advisory panels, graduate recruitment, research and consultancy, and student projects. Haywood and Maki (1992) identify a conceptual model of the education–employment interface for the tourism industry, based on the expectations and perceptions of a number of stakeholders. There are different hurdles to have interaction among both. First, the industry tends to regard training and education as an alien concept (Messenger, 1991), whereby training is not seen as an important contributor to competitiveness and profitability. Second, few hurdles to entry mean that specialist qualifications are not a requirement (DfEE, 2000), and a career in tourism is often seen as a low status career (Shepherd and Cooper, 1994). It is also found that managers in the tourism industry who have often not had a higher education themselves tend not to value educational background (Ritchie, 1990; Shepherd and Cooper, 1994). At last, there are problems in the attitudes of tourism academicians in terms of striking a balance between industry and academic requirements (Baum, 1998; Cooper, Scales and Westlake, 1992). Hannam et al (2004) surveyed MSc program (Tourism) at University of Sunderland and found that professional skills and information technology skills need to be improved. Moreover, career guidance is own responsibility as well as the course team.

Okumus and Yagci (2005), master program in tourism education in Turkey was started in 1969. Even first formal program in higher education was started in 1965. However, dearth of qualified academicians, curriculum not goal oriented, limited internship opportunities and to retain human resources are problems faced by academia and industry. These problems are also identified in number of studies from across the globe (e.g., Hobson, 1999; Theuns and Rasheed, 1991; Cooper et al. 1992; King, 1994; Amoah and Baum, 1997; Barrows and Bosselman, 1999; Christou, 1999; Dale and Robinson, 2001; Knowles *et al.*, 2003; Sigala and Baum, 2003). Ernawati (2003) criticised that there is minimal participation of industry representatives in tourism curriculum design by the academicians. It leads to the mismatch in supply-demand relationship. Also this scenario does not reflect the skills

and knowledge of tourism graduates in industry. Sheldon et al. (2008) further described demographic, environmental, technological, economic, cultural, and governmental factors will dramatically change tourism education during 2010-2030. Cooper (2010) has identified that there is a persistent gap between tourism educators, trainers and employers, and tourism sector failed to develop the workforce for the knowledge economy and persists with archaic human resource (HR) practices. In particular, tourism education is living in the past and have not adapted to the needs of 21st century. Sheldon et al. (2011), has explored that The Tourism Education Futures Initiative (TEFI) seeks to develop tourism graduates with values “global citizenship and optimism for a better world” (p.2). In Indian context, the following problems are existed in the present Tourism Education according to Dahiya (2013),

- Acceptance of limited research proposal in tourism education
- Borrowed from Western countries
- Confusion over nature of tourism education (vocational/professional/professional)
- Decade old syllabus into practice in educational institutes.
- Exploitation of graduates during internship leads to drop out from tourism industry
- Lack of will power to promote tourism education by government
- Multiple authorities are involved in program development of tourism education
- No independent faculty in educational organization
- No international institutional co-operations
- Non- standardization of Curriculum (courses of studies)
- Non uniformity in qualification to recruit the faculty
- Non-availability of resource persons
- Non-standardized nomenclature of courses
- Similar component of syllabus across different courses,
- Vacuum of the senior faculty
- Varied organizational structures among different institutions

There is a huge gap between academic training and professional requirement. Requalification and re-specialization are the requirement to compete the global race.

As argued by Taillon (2014), tourism is an academic study and global network of researchers and there is need to condense the empirical data of tourism into tourism theories. Lack of infrastructure, no students/teachers exchange programs, lack of corporation and consolidations among industry and academia is widening the gap between industry requirements and academia output (Dhanoa, 2014). Morelletto

(2014), explored that teacher was the source of knowledge in traditional classroom while in this information society source of knowledge is not limited to teachers only. Morelletto (2014) supported Polillo, who has supported the online learning eco-system i.e. among the advancement of technology there needs to connect knowledge with students, and academicians as a facilitator.

Figure 2.5: New age classroom

Source: Polillo (2013 cited by Morelletto, 2014)

Now traditional classrooms are connected to digital source of information/learning. Tourism education is being faced problems raised from reproduction of tourism forms, financial crises, ideology conflicts, technology and climate change.

The parent tourism graduates failed to perform in industry and those who (tourism graduates) performed well industry, it was because of their lifelong learning spirit (George, 2017). Moreover, Shree et al. (2019) has divided skill level into four levels. India skill report 2019, only 45.6% graduates are employable. Formally skilled workers in India to the total work force is 4.69%. While it is 24%, 52%, 68%, 75%, 80% and 96% in case of China, US, UK, Germany, Japan and South Korea respectively. The benefits of interaction between higher education institutions and industry are widespread. Academia-industry linkage is a complex network. Tourism industry constitutes multiple components which vary in size and domains. It creates confusion between curriculum (specialist or general program) development and industry requirements. It is also a challenge that there is employability to all tourism graduates. Education level of employers (less formal education) and tourism graduates is also a major issue. It can be inferred that there is need to identify the potential interest of the stakeholders and participation in curriculum development,

professional experiences, exposure to graduates as per their qualification, continuum knowledge development among academicians and professionals through alternative stakeholders. Authors argued that there is need to liberalize the tourism education in the country for higher gain from tourism. It can be asserted that for the growth of tourism in a country/province/region/destination, the quality of human resource plays a role of pivotal.

2.9 Future of Tourism Education

In 1960s economic perspective was involved with respect to tourism research. But modern tourism research has been adopted new paradigm shift to research in the field of environment, socio-cultural and psychology. Maclaurin (2005), “The future of tourism education will likely include the increasing use of electronic and other distance learning technologies” (p.23). Technology has influenced the tourism as well as tourism education also. In this dynamic tourism world, the “Tourism educators will be asked with the responsibility of developing future industry leaders capable of sustaining and growing Canada’s tourism industry” (p.24). It is expected from all across the globe and not limited to Canadian tourism industry only but it is clear that advancement in technology will establish new paradigms in tourism education as well as industry. There is necessity to widen the area of tourism education as the forms of tourism are proliferating and array of tourism impacts is for reaching. Moreover, there is need of local, regional, national and international perspectives for the assessment of tourism development to know the scale of impact through tourism (Wall and Mathieson 2006). Tourism is a fiercely competitive market, requiring skills, talent and enterprise (Cameron, 2010). Goodman and Sprague (1991) suggested that modification and modernization of tourism programs is the need of future. Future education must have as agenda to continuous learning, new knowledge and design their life as well as society. Kuruvilla et al (2011) opined that vocational education has lack of futuristic approach and based on contemporary need of the industry. Tourism courses in Greece in higher education are free and there is no private university. Marine tourism and Agro-tourism are primary courses there. Cohen and Cohen (2012), further, during 1987-2012 the world had shifted from closed economies → open economies → tourism driven economies. Revealed tourism was considered as western phenomenon but it has relocated to China, India, Brazil and

Hong Kong because of liberalized economies, tourism is now international phenomenon. The Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), economic recession, terrorism, environmental issues are the major factors which affect the phenomenon of tourism i.e. volume of tourism industry, employment and forex. It can be themed as tourism problems are destination based and need to develop own solutions. Derouiche (2012) speculated that during 2002-2012, great web-accessibility, e-tourism, online itineraries, natural disaster and health issues will impact the future tourist demand. It has led to the change in traveller's preferences and perception about holidays and leisure.

Derouiche (2012) revealed, during 2012-2022 following trends are applicable for future tourism:

1. New emerging inbound and outbound destination: "Eastern Europe, with many countries joining the EU, Asia and South America will play a major role as leading inbound destinations since they excite and arouse the interest of many travellers" (p.2) and found, India and China are emerging outbound markets. It implies that there is need for in-depth studies on tourists' travel needs.
2. In knowledge based economy, the travellers are aware about negative impacts of tourism on environment. So they are travelling responsibly which is heading towards green/nature-based/sustainable tourism.
3. Climate change has an impact on tourists' purchasing behaviour as well as a threat to humanity. There will be emergence of new transport medium and short haul trips within same continent or geographical region will emerge.
4. Purpose of travelling will change during upcoming decade from traditional way to travelling for mission i.e. Travel for learnings, volunteering tourism. "As a result, tour operators are now becoming specialists rather than generalists" (p.3.).
5. Social media will be the consumer generated media.
6. Tourism destinations, with cooperation among different stakeholders of tourism over safety and security of population and visitors, tourist will travel for such destinations. It is need of the hour to develop policies on this issue.

7. Human resource makes and breaks the experiences. There is need for large human resources across the globe but qualified ones. There is need to upgrade present workforce. Sustainable workforce can be developed through education, training and migration policies. He suggested, “Tourism education policy should be developed and designed by tourism entity not by ministry of education” (p.5).
8. “Creating human resource councils that address the needs of the tourism sector at a local, regional or national levels and aiming at reducing the gap between what is offered and what is needed, and focusing on quality control and related issues”(p.5)

But the ongoing outbreak of COVID-19 has put the tourism industry into uncertainty but government are taking the recovery of tourism industry on priority bases. The webinars on different aspects of tourism industry, future of tourism industry and tourism education are on rise. The countries across the globe are working on innovative ideas to restore the tourism activities e.g. social bubble in Australia and New Zealand. The 21st century has entered the 4th industrial revolution. The technologies like cloud computing, mobile application, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have changed the profile of Human Resource (HR). Human resource and technology are the great contributors for the productivity of tourism sector. To compete the futuristic demand of tourism industry, there is need to look into “careful planning, positioning clear goals, curriculum planning, integrating hospitality/tourism curriculum, alliances and collaboration, and strengthening tourism and hospitality research” (Dahiya, 2013). He opined that there is need for implement above mentioned reforms. It implies the growth in global tourism education is leading towards the competitive tourism industry. There is need to improve Indian tourism education system. Morellato, 2014, Generation Z has stimulated higher education institutes to reform towards enlarged digital competency rather than just for digital skills. In information society, there is need to “developing digital competence in tourism education by considering new technologies and a cooperative learning paradigm” (p.184).

The field of tourism education scholarship is wide open and the thirst for fertile intellectual pursuits. There is more need for scholarship in the field of tourism

for more soul searching discussions, and philosophical debates are required as tourism education moves forward in the constantly changing and uncertain future environment (Hsu, 2015). The tourism education should have global perspective, need to integrate humanities, values, and multidisciplinary approaches into tourism curriculum, rethink western-centric and market oriented approaches, explore the possibilities of experiential and transformational education, and adopt pedagogical innovations. AI and ML have been applied for training process, assessment process, recruitment process and prediction process (Padmanabhan, 2018). The internet technology has changed the tourism business (Minghetti and Buhalis, 2010; Pan and Fesenmaier, 2000). The technology can play an important role in internationalisation of tourism programs through distance learning programs. In addition, Nimse (2016) has suggested that Internationalisation of education can be promoted through students and teachers exchange programme. There is need for innovative programs for curriculum development, networking among academicians, government, local and national agencies for better tourism education. Rifai (2016), has expressed that ‘travel revolution’, which has positioned tourism as fundamental element of our lives and ‘boom of new technologies’ in the last decades has changed the game of tourism in the Asia and the Pacific. Information and Communication Technologies have made people travel more easily. Tourism education with Information and Communication Technologies within the tourism sector need to be studied to make balance among human resource and contemporary tourism services. During 2010-2030, technological innovation will change the tourism world and it is evident from above studies. Traditional class rooms were limited to teachers and books but contemporary classrooms are not confined and are connected to vast world of information through internet. Technology is influencing the consumer behaviour also. Digital competence is a key driver to flourish the entrepreneurship, communication and networking, promotes creative culture, future analysis, and enhance employability of tourism graduates. Therefore it leads to the conclusion that there is need to incorporate technology in tourism education and investment in technology-led tourism.

If tourism professionals are not aware of these technologies, they will definitely have competitive disadvantage. This is the era of competition for existence between technologies and human resources. So to sustain in competition, contemporary technologies can be incorporated in tourism education. Mphuthing

(2019) argued that it's a brilliant decision to hire smart employees than employers. It also added that investment in skill development, change in traditional recruitment system, new education and career model as automation is on apace and re-skilling of employees will define the future scenario of work. According to online magazine, The Knowledge Review (2019) in present teaching era academicians are struggling to make students concentrate on their studies as well as to teach them. The system of teachings needs to change. Virtual reality, online courses and learning management system are influencing the education system. One of India's largest Hotel School's Chain, the International Institute of Hotel Management (2019) was awarded as India's Best Education Brand 2018 by Economic Times. IIHM is leading the hospitality education because of international internship, cultural diversity, multicity/ multinational campuses, network of more than 10000 alumni across the globe, technology and information technology as the bedrock of hospitality education and pro-active integrated curriculum which helps to respond, update and adapt quickly to global changes and job requirements. The emerging inbound/outbound tourism destinations (COVID-19 has inverted the data), great web accessibility, travel for a mission, sustainability bent of mind, upskilling of human resources, cooperation among tourism industry stakeholders, specified tourism entity to develop tourism education, social media as consumer generated media, climate change and knowledge based economy are the key factors to decide future and reshape tourism education across the economies, irrespective of its size.

2.10 Tourism Education Curriculum and Skills.

McKercher (2002), universities education in Australia shifted to practical and applied program since capitalization of tourism industry was goal. Tribe (2002) has analysed that "The curriculum aim for the graduating philosophic practitioner is to promote a balance between satisfying the demands of business and those of the wider tourism society and world" (p.340). The context of tourism education is not limited to provide manpower to the tourism industry but tourism for a better world.

Figure 2.6: The Philosophic Practitioner

Aims	Better tourism service
Roles	Better tourism world
Ends	Occupational competence

	Stewardship of tourism
Stance	Liberal: stakeholders and places Reflection Action
Epistemology	Business interdisciplinarity Extradisciplinarity Multidisciplinarity General interdisciplinarity Knowing in vocational action Practical wisdom
Rationality	Technical Communicative
Ideology	To be exposed (such as vocationalism, academicism)
Issues and values	An unbounded view of tourism's world, including tourism satisfaction, efficiency, profit, effectiveness, productivity, environment, justice, equality, aesthetics, ethics, culture and history
Tourism interests	Tourism's society: tourists, business and non-business interests

Source: Tribe (2002)

Under Bologna Declaration, “Slovenian education institutions are trying to internationalise their programmes, foster student and professor exchanges, arrange joint programmes with foreign universities, as well as international cooperation in curriculum development and research” (Mihalic 2004, p.93). Pierce (2005), revealed that the development of tourism education in Australia is an output because of “a strong research-education nexus and the consolidation rather than loss of the degree offerings over time” (p.251). Horng and Lee (2006) have explored Tourism education in Taiwan has divided into academic higher education and technical/vocational education. Investment in citizens of country and growth in domestic tourism market leads to the growth of tourism education. To address the future issues of tourism institutes are into networking, change in curriculum, diversification of programs, integrating hospitality and tourism courses and investment into research. Sheldon et al (2008) have mentioned that global tourism education institution i.e. Tourism Education Future Initiative is creating a value based curriculum to produce “responsible future tourism leaders” (p.67). Sheldon et al. (2008), have explored and categorized the requisite skills for students entering the tourism world into four categories as following;

Table 2.2: Skills Requirement in Tourism Industry

<p><i>Destination Stewardship Skills</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management of real and virtual networks • Knowledge sharing skills. • Ability to respect and work with all stakeholders. • Managing complex adaptive systems. • Environmental management skills. 	<p><i>Political and Ethical Skills</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical behaviour, demonstration and motivation. • Integration of basic human values into the workplace. • Lobbying and the ability to influence the political process.
<p><i>Enhanced Human Resource Skills</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team building. • Effective listening and negotiation. • Motivation and leadership. • Working with distributed, virtual project teams. • Emotional intelligence. 	<p><i>Dynamic Business Skills</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexibility, Multitasking, Critical thinking • Optimal use of common sense, • Innovation/entrepreneurship, • Communication skills using new multimedia technologies, Cross-cultural competencies, • Risk identification, estimation, and control • Avoiding problems rather than solving them

Source: Sheldon et al. (2008, pp.66-67).

It can be concluded from proposed skills that educators need to develop left the brain thinking as well as emotional intelligence among upcoming future tourism professionals. IIM Sirmour (2020) has released the admission broacher for MBA THM session 2020-2022, and has mentioned that “curriculum pedagogy shall be a combination of lectures, flip classroom sessions, case studies, online resources, field work, project assignments, lab sessions, etc. The programme combines to offer core business knowledge and management skills, including Entrepreneurship, Special Interest Tourism, Tourism Planning, Tourism Analytics, Contemporary Hotel and Travel Management, and the like”. The development of tourism industry across the world initiated the need for tourism professionals and demanded requisite change in curriculum although industry needs to influence it. Tourism Management is less adopted over Hospitality Management after 10+2 year of schooling. The different regulatory agencies in India for tourism education and hospitality education, instead of one body. India is a destination for all type of tourists but our tourism education is failed to produce entrepreneurship bent of minds, spirit of product development, lack of avenues for tourism graduates in policy and planning, diversification of tourism programs, lack of will among bureaucrats due to limited tenure, appointment of non-tourism background professionals in tourism institutions, a huge time gap among tourism policy recommendation and policy implementation and frequent dropout rate among tourism graduates from tourism industry.

2.11 Research Gap

The present thesis titled as “Tourism Education in India: Perception of Academicians and Industry Professionals” finds myriad of gaps in order to direct tourism education in the country by and large.

It is concluded that there is huge mismatch in the nature of education imparted through tourism programs and its applicability in the industry. In many universities, the department of tourism studies is not functioning as an independent entity. There is a lack of updated knowledge amongst faculty and a shortage of faculty as well. Tourism is aligned with at many institutions with other disciplines like Geography, History, Museology, Archaeology, Commerce, Culture, Rural Development, Extension Centre, Art, Sociology, Management etc.

One of the major drawbacks is with regard to curriculum development of tourism programs. Curriculum is not up to the demand and requirement of contemporary tourism industry. The paradigms of tourism industry appear to be unparalleled with the manpower producing agencies like universities and other institutions. A strong bridge along with research and discussion is the requirement of the hour. One national level major issue constantly/frequently floating in the surface of tourism education as well as industry requirement is that there is a huge lack of principled, visionary, entrepreneurial bent of minds.

It directly spreads the message that our top level institutions have not been successful to produce such kind of visionary minds who could compete internationally. It indicates that, on the name of human resources our institutes are just producing a labour force who could earn or give benefits to the capitalists of tourism industry. In all levels of undergraduates/post graduates courses the kind of similar syllabus is repeatedly being taught by extending the same programs. There is nothing new to learn when scholars/students enter higher education.

In international level, Indian research in tourism has not trust worthy recognition. Many scholars keep raising questions against Indian researchers in tourism education (e.g. George, 2017).

The following research gap is identified after literature review

- Several studies on Tourism Education have been carried out in Developed economies where tourism is firmly established. However there is a striking lack of studies in countries where Tourism is a relatively new discipline.
- In India, the limited research on tourism education has only concentrated in identifying the institutions offering tourism education and the nature of programs being offered.
- Studies on tourism education in the country have only concentrated on tourism education delivering institutes
- Tourism Education has not been studied from the angel of industry providers' requirements.
- Quality of tourism education being imparted in India has not been a focus of study
- No comparative study on has been carried out till date to assess the perception of quality of tourism education in the eyes of academicians as compared to industry professional in India

The present study revolves around addressing the above research gap issues.

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